

Incidence of Seed-Borne Fungal Pathogens in Farm-Saved Common Bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) Seeds in Kagera Region, Tanzania

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Abstract

Common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) is a vital source of protein and income for smallholder farmers in Tanzania. However, its productivity remains low, partly due to seed-borne diseases. This study assessed the incidence of seed-borne fungal pathogens in farm-saved bean seeds and examined their effects on common bean seed quality in Kagera Region, Tanzania. A total of 180 seed samples were collected from six villages across three major bean-producing districts. In Misenyi District, sampling was done in Kyaka Ward (Kyaka and Kashaba villages) and Nsungu Ward (Nsungu and Bulifani villages). In Karagwe District, seeds were obtained from Nyakasimbi Ward (Nyakasimbi and Bujara villages) and Ihanda Ward (Ihanda and Kandegesho villages). In Ngora District, samples were collected from Kirushya Ward (Kasangwe and Mwivuzza villages) and Rusumo Ward (Mshikamano and Kasharazi villages). Standard seed health testing was conducted using the blotter method in accordance with ISTA guidelines to evaluate seed purity, moisture content, germination percentage, and fungal contamination. The experiment was laid out in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with three replications, and data were statistically analyzed using R software (R Core Team, 2024). Results revealed highly significant differences ($p < 0.001$) in fungal incidence across the sites. A strong negative correlation ($r = -0.65$) was observed between fungal infection and germination rate, seedling vigor, and overall seed quality. Among the pathogens identified, *Colletotrichum dematium* emerged as the most prevalent, with incidences of 4% in Ngora, 3% in Karagwe, and 0.5% in Misenyi. Contrary to expectations, *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum* (the causal agent of anthracnose) was not detected in any of the stored common bean seed samples. Fungal assays frequently yielded saprophytic isolates, including *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus*. Correlation analysis indicated that increased seed moisture content was significantly and positively associated with reduced seed viability ($r = 0.49$, $p < 0.01$). Furthermore, the level of fungal contamination showed a significant negative correlation with root development ($r = -0.42$, $p < 0.01$). These findings underscore the need to strengthen seed systems by promoting the use of certified seeds, improving post-harvest handling practices, ensuring proper drying and short-term storage, and encouraging the adoption of effective seed treatment protocols. Addressing these factors is crucial for reducing the transmission of seed-borne disease, improving seed quality, supporting sustainable bean production, and food security among smallholder farmers in Tanzania.

Keywords: Common bean, anthracnose, seed quality, farm-saved seeds, fungal pathogens.

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Introduction

Common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) is one of the most widely cultivated grain legume in the world and serves as a key source of dietary protein, calories, and income for millions of households, especially in developing countries (Kiptoo, 2020). Globally, the crop is cultivated on approximately 33 million hectares, with an annual production of about 28.9 million metric tons (Kiptoo, 2020). Africa accounts for 7.8 million hectares, roughly 25% of the global bean cultivation area, with more than 100 million households relying on beans for income, food security and nutritional sustenance (Kadege et al., 2022; Mukankusi et al., 2019). In Tanzania, common bean ranks the third most widely cultivated food crop after maize and cassava, largely grown by smallholder farmers who primarily depend on farm-saved seeds for production (Farrow and Muthoni, 2020; Mukankusi et al., 2019). Despite its agronomic and socio-economic importance, common bean production is hindered by various challenges, including abiotic and biotic stresses. Among the most destructive biotic threats is anthracnose disease, caused by the fungal pathogen *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum*, which is especially severe in regions with cool and moist conditions that favor its development and spread (Kadege et al., 2022). The pathogen infects multiple plant parts leaves, stems, pods, and seeds, resulting in significant yield loss and deterioration in seed quality (Dushimeyesu et al., 2023). Reports indicate that anthracnose can reduce seed quality by 10.52% to 57.76%, lower seed weight per pod by 21.93% to 68.77%, and cause overall yield losses of up to 95% under epidemic conditions (Dushimeyesu et al., 2023). Moreover, a reduction of up to 40% in seed germination due to anthracnose infection has been documented, with serious implications for the availability and marketability of quality seed (Ciofini et al., 2022).

The reliance on farm-saved seeds among Tanzanian smallholders has exacerbated the persistence and spread of seed-borne pathogens. The common practice among most smallholder farmers of reusing farm-saved seeds harvested from infected parent plants inadvertently contributes to the perpetuation of seed-borne pathogens. This cycle ensures the reintroduction of inoculum into the field environment, thereby initiating a new disease cycle during subsequent planting seasons (Abera et al., 2020; Kiptoo, 2020). Alarmingly, only 18% of farmers in affected regions actively implement any form of disease control, contributing to the continued prevalence of seed-borne infected seeds in informal seed systems (Kadege et al., 2024; Kadege et al., 2022). The shortage of certified seeds further compounds the problem, forcing farmers to rely on poor-quality seeds that are frequently infected due to inadequate post-harvest handling and disease management (Breen et al., 2024). In some regions, seed-borne outbreaks have driven seed price increases of up to 20%, placing further economic strain on farmers and consumers alike (McLaughlin et al., 2023). In addition seed-borne fungal pathogens have been identified in common bean seeds, including *Fusarium pallidoroseum*, *F. solani*, *F. moniliforme*, *Phoma* spp., and *Phaeoisariopsis griseola*, all of which contribute to reduced seed viability and plant establishment (Okello et al., 2010; Chirwa et al., 2014). These pathogens are frequently associated with poor on-farm seed storage conditions and the absence of adequate seed treatment protocols (Mwang'ombe et al., 2007).

This study examines the association between seed-borne pathogen incidence and fundamental seed physiological parameters, specifically assessing germination rate, root and shoot development, and overall seedling vigor. The primary goal is to generate robust evidence-based recommendations for effective disease management and comprehensive seed quality enhancement. The derived outcomes are intended to directly advise smallholder bean farmers in Tanzania on improved agronomic practices, focusing particularly on seed selection, storage, and treatment. Ultimately, these targeted interventions aim to

mitigate seed-borne disease transmission, thereby increasing agricultural productivity and strengthening food and income security within the region (Kadege et al., 2022).

Materials and Methods

Description of Study Area

The samples were collected in three districts of Kagera Region, namely, Missenyi, Karagwe, and Ngara as illustrated in Figure 1. Kagera region is situated in northwest Tanzania, just below the equator, between latitudes 1°00' and 2°45' S and longitudes 30°25' and 32°40' E. Ngara District is located in northwestern Tanzania (2°38' S, 30°41' E), at an elevation of about 1 800 m with annual rainfall ranging from 800 mm to 1 400 mm and temperatures between 12°C and 30°C. Karagwe District is located at 1°26'15" S, 31°10'25" E. The area experiences average temperatures ranging from 18°C to 25°C and annual rainfall between 163 mm and 800 mm (Fick and Hijmans, 2017). Missenyi district lies between latitudes 01°00' and 01°30' S and longitudes 30°48' and 31°49' E, at an altitude of 1 100 –1 400 meters above sea level, receiving 700–1 000 mm of rainfall annually, with temperatures ranging from 16°C to 28°C.

Laboratory Experiment

A laboratory experiment was conducted at the Plant Pathology Laboratory of Sokoine University of Agriculture (SUA) in Morogoro Region, Tanzania. The SUA is located at 6°51'5" S and 37°39'25" E, at an altitude of 500 – 600 m above sea level, with an annual rainfall of 600 – 1 000 mm and mean temperatures of 20 – 30 °C.

Figure 1. Map of the Study Area Showing Surveyed Wards within the Missenyi (A), Karagwe (B), and Ngara (C) Districts, and the Location of the Laboratory Site at SUA (D) in Tanzania

Determination of Fungal Incidence on Farm-Saved Bean Seeds

Farm-saved seed sample collection

To assess the incidence of seed-borne fungal pathogens in common bean production, a purposive sampling technique was used to select three major bean-producing districts in Kagera Region of Tanzania. The selected districts were Missenyi, Karagwe, and Ngara, chosen for their high levels of bean cultivation and the widespread reliance on farm-saved seeds among smallholder farmers which contributes to the persistence and spread of seed-borne fungal pathogens in smallholder farming systems.

These districts contribute significantly to the region's overall bean production and exemplify the common agricultural and seed management conditions under which seed-borne pathogens are likely to affect productivity. Within each selected district, two wards were purposively selected based on their prominence in bean production and extensive use of farm-saved seeds. Subsequently, two villages from each ward were also purposively selected using similar criteria, with guidance from district and ward-level agricultural extension officers. This targeted approach ensured the inclusion of production zones most representative of the study objectives, particularly areas where seed-borne disease risks are likely to be higher due to continuous seed recycling.

To identify individual respondents, a multi-stage random sampling approach was employed (FAO, 2022). Within each selected village, 15 farmers were randomly selected from a verified list of active bean growers, provided by the local agricultural extension office. Each farmer provided two seed samples, resulting in 60 farmers per district and a total of 180 farmers across the three districts. Consequently, a total of 360 seed samples were collected for analysis, ensuring sufficient representation across the study area and alignment with the study objectives.

The sample size was obtained using the formula (Cochran, 1977):

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \times p(1 - p)}{e^2} \quad (1)$$

Where, n is the sample size, Z is the Z-score corresponding to the desired confidence level (1.96 for 95% confidence), p is the estimated proportion of farmers using farm-saved seeds, and e is the margin of error (set at 5% in this study).

The inclusion criteria for farmer selection required active involvement in bean cultivation for at least in the past three consecutive cropping seasons, reliance on farm-saved seeds as the primary source for planting, and demonstrated willingness to voluntarily participate in the study by providing seed samples. Each participating farmer provided two distinct farm-saved bean seed varieties, resulting in the collection of 360 seed samples. Approximately 500 grams of seeds were obtained per sample, packed in clean, clearly labeled paper bags and dispatched to the African Seed Health Laboratory at Sokoine University of Agriculture (SUA) for laboratory analysis.

To ensure adequate genetic and varietal representation, seed samples of the same variety collected from each district were bulked together to form composite working samples. This procedure resulted in the creation of nine composite seed landraces: Rozikoko, Chibeho, Njanogolori, Soya, Kanyobwa, Shusha, Kaduli, Wifi-Nyegela, and Mshingile Akati.

For subsequent analyses, the composite samples of each variety were used for both seed quality and growth parameter testing. Similarly, disease assessments were conducted on the composite samples of each variety from each district. Each composite variety was independently examined in the laboratory to

determine the incidence of seed-borne fungal pathogens, ensuring consistent and representative evaluation across all study locations.

Experimental Design, Treatments and Data Collection

Fungal incidence

The incidence of seed-borne fungal pathogens in farm-saved bean seeds was assessed using a combination of visual inspection, the agar plate incubation method, and the blotter method. For visual assessment, a random sample of 200 seeds from each composite variety was examined under a stereomicroscope to identify visible symptoms of infection, including discoloration, lesions, shriveling, and other physical abnormalities suggestive of fungal contamination. Since active fungal growth is rarely visible on dried seeds, this approach provided only preliminary indications of infection.

To confirm and identify fungal pathogens, seeds were incubated on the blotter method to detect fungal presence. From each composite seed sample, 10 seeds were placed in Petri dishes lined with moistened sterile blotter paper and incubated in darkness at 20 °C for seven days, after which fungal structures indicative of infection were examined and recorded. The experimental setup followed a two-factor factorial arrangement in a completely randomized design (CRD) with three replications per treatment. The two factors were: Location (Missenyi, Karagwe, Ngara), and bean landraces (Rozikoko, Chibeho, Njanogolori, Soya, Kanyobwa, Shusha, Kaduli, Wifi-Nyegela, Mshingile Akati). This factorial arrangement produced 27 treatment combinations, each replicated three times, yielding a total of 81 experimental units. For each experimental unit, 200 seeds were assessed to evaluate seed quality, seedling growth, and the incidence of seed-borne fungal pathogens. This design enabled simultaneous evaluation of the main effects of district and variety, as well as their interaction, thereby enhancing the reliability, validity, and interpretability of the results. The presence of pathogenic fungi was confirmed based on depressed spores with well-defined margins. Acervuli with dark brown setae and conidia, observed under 25x and 200x magnification. (Appendix 1)

Fungal incidence (%) for each variety was calculated using the formula:

$$Incidence = \frac{\text{Number of infected seeds}}{\text{Total number of seeds sown}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Seed Purity, Viability, Moisture, and Seedling Vigor

A laboratory experiment was conducted to assess seed quality parameters as affected by fungal infestation. For seed quality analysis, seeds of the same variety were homogenized using a seed divider to form nine composite samples. Each sample consisted of 200 seeds, subdivided into four replicates of 50 seeds each.

Seed germination test

Seeds were surface-sterilized using 0.5% sodium hypochlorite for 3 minutes, then rinsed twice with sterile distilled water. They were sown in sterilized sand-filled pots at an equal sowing depth under controlled conditions at the SUA Plant Pathology Laboratory. The tests were conducted in an environment chamber maintained at 25 ± 2 °C, with a 12-hour photoperiod and 70 – 80% relative humidity. Watering was done uniformly to maintain optimal moisture levels without waterlogging. Seedling emergence was recorded daily from Day 5 to Day 9, in accordance with the International Seed Testing Association (ISTA, 2021) guidelines for common bean germination testing. This 9-day observation period reflects the time in during which viable seeds are expected to emerge under optimal conditions.

Germination percentage was determined by recording the number of normal seedlings that emerged within the evaluation period. Seedling evaluation was conducted in accordance with ISTA (2021) guidelines, wherein germination was defined as the emergence of a normal seedling capable of sustained growth. Abnormal seedlings and dead seeds were excluded from the germination count because they lack the capacity to establish healthy plants under field conditions. Germination test percentage was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Germination Percent} = \frac{\text{Number of germinated seeds}}{\text{Total seeds sown}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Seedling vigor

Seedling vigor was assessed by measuring the shoot and root lengths of normal seedlings using a graduated transparent plastic ruler. Germination assessment was conducted on the ninth day after sowing (9DAS). This measurement represented the final germination count, marking the conclusion of the test period as no further normal seedling emergence was anticipated, in accordance with International Seed Testing Association (ISTA, 2021) guidelines. Seedlings were carefully uprooted from the sand, and any adhering particles were gently removed using distilled water. Shoot length was measured from the collar (junction of root and shoot) to the tip of the first true leaf, while root length was measured from the collar to the tip of the primary root. Each measurement was recorded for all normal seedlings within each replicate, and mean values were calculated to determine seedling vigor per treatment.

The vigor index was computed using the following formula:

$$\text{Vigor Index} = (\text{Mean Root Length} + \text{Mean Shoot Length}) \times \text{Germination Percentage} \quad (4)$$

Seed purity

Seed purity was determined by weighing each seed sample before and after removing inert materials, debris, broken, malformed, and diseased seeds. The percentage of pure seeds was calculated from the cleaned sample. The clean seed portion was weighed, and purity was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Purity (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of pure seeds}}{\text{Weight of original seed sample}} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

Moisture content

Seed moisture content was determined using the constant oven drying method at 133 °C for 4 hours (ISTA, 2021). The weight of the empty Petri dish was recorded as M_1 , the weight of the Petri dish plus seeds before drying was recorded as M_2 , and the weight of the Petri dish plus seeds after drying was recorded as M_3 . The moisture content (%) was then calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Moisture Content (\%)} = \frac{(M_2 - M_3)}{(M_2 - M_1)} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

Data Analysis

The collected data on fungal incidence, germination percentage, shoot length, root length, and seedling vigor index were systematically compiled and subjected to statistical analysis using R statistical software (version 4.5.0 R Core Team, 2024). Before inferential analysis, the assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variances were evaluated using the Shapiro–Wilk and Levene’s tests, respectively (Razali and Wah, 2011). Where significant effects were detected at $p < 0.05$, post hoc mean separation was conducted using Tukey’s Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) test to compare treatment means. Graphical visualizations were developed using the ggplot2 package to illustrate the comparative effects of seed quality parameters and fungal infection levels (Wickham, 2016).

Results

Seed-Borne Fungal Incidence

Fungal infection on farm-saved bean seeds

Several seed-borne fungal pathogens were detected across the sampled farm-saved bean seed lots. *Fusarium pallidoroseum* was the most dominant species, with an incidence of 12.5%, indicating its widespread occurrence in the region. Other common fungal pathogens included *Fusarium moniliforme* (10.0%) and *Colletotrichum dematium* (7.5%). In addition, *Fusarium oxysporum* (6.0%), *Fusarium solani* (5.5%), and *Phasariopsis griseola* (4.5%) were observed at moderate levels, alongside *Fusarium equiseti* (3.0%) and *Macrophomina phaseolina* (2.5%). Less frequently occurring fungi included *Cercospora kikuchii* (1.0%), reflecting the diverse fungal presence among the seed samples (Plate 1).

Plate 1. Microscopic Observation of Incubated Seeds: (A) Fungal Spores Observation under Microscope, (B) *Aspergillus Niger* and *A. flavus* Spores, (C) Fungal Growth on Seeds, and (D) Conidia of *Colletotrichum dematium*

Furthermore, the findings confirmed the presence of saprophytic fungi, specifically *Aspergillus niger* (4.5%) and *Aspergillus flavus* (4.0%), detected in multiple seed lots at varying levels. Interestingly, *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum*, the causal agent of anthracnose, was not detected in any of the examined seed samples. This suggests that the pathogen may either be absent from the tested lots or present at levels below the detection threshold. Nevertheless, continuous field-level surveillance is recommended to validate its epidemiological status in the region.

Fungal seed incidence by District

The total fungal seed incidence by district is presented in Figure 2, showing significant variation ($p < 0.0001$) among the three districts. Karagwe district recorded the highest incidence levels, with *Aspergillus niger* (4.0% incidence) and *Aspergillus flavus* (2.5% incidence) being the most common fungi detected. These results further revealed variations in fungal incidence (FI %) across districts (Fig. 2). Karagwe district recorded the highest overall fungal incidence, indicating a greater severity of seed infection within that sample set. The most frequently isolated fungal species in Karagwe were *Aspergillus niger* (4.0%) and *Aspergillus flavus* (2.5%). The presence of *A. flavus* is of particular concern due to its capacity to produce aflatoxins (Bennett and Klich, 2003; Klich, 2007). In contrast, Missenyi and Ngara districts exhibited a more diverse fungal profile, with several fungal species detected, each contributing between 0.5% and 1.5% to the total incidence. This indicates

that although infection levels per species were relatively low compared to Karagwe, the presence of multiple species reflects a higher fungal diversity in these districts.

Figure 2. Incidence of Fungal Species Identified from Farm-Saved Bean Seeds across Three Districts

Seed fungal infection and incidence by variety

Analysis of seed-borne fungal infection incidence among the tested common bean landraces revealed statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$), indicating differential resistance levels (Fig. 3, Fig. 4). The highest mean incidence was recorded in Mshingile Akati ($1.8 \pm 0.84\%$) and Wifi-Nyegela ($1.8 \pm 0.63\%$)

corresponding to 13 and 12 infected seeds out of 200 (6.5% and 6.0%) infected seeds, respectively, and characterized by infection from multiple fungal species including *Fusarium moniliforme*, *F. solani*, *Phasariopsis griseola*, and *Macrophomina phaseolina*. Soya also displayed a relatively high incidence ($1.4 \pm 0.56\%$, 8 cases; 4.0%) (Fig. 3), predominantly associated with *Aspergillus niger*, *F. equiseti*, and *M. phaseolina*. Conversely, the lowest incidence was observed in Rozikoko ($0.6 \pm 0.30\%$, 1 case; 0.5%) and Kaduli ($0.9 \pm 0.56\%$, 4 cases; 2.0%), where all detected pathogens occurred at very low frequencies.

Post-hoc Tukey's HSD test ($p < 0.05$) grouped Mshingile Akati, Wifi-Nyegela, and Soya into a statistically similar high-incidence cluster, while Rozikoko and Kaduli formed the lowest-incidence cluster. This observed variation strongly suggests inherent genetic differences in resistance, with the high-incidence group being more susceptible and the low-incidence group displaying comparatively higher resistance to seed-borne fungal infections.

Table 1. Incidence of Seed-Borne Fungal Infections across Common Bean Landraces

Variety	Mean Incidence (%)	Cases (number)	% of Infected Seeds	Major Fungal Species Detected
Mshingile Akati	1.8 ± 0.84	13	6.5	<i>Fusarium moniliforme</i> , <i>Fusarium solani</i> , <i>Phasariopsis griseola</i> , <i>Macrophomina phaseolina</i>
Wifi-Nyegela	1.8 ± 0.63	12	6.0	<i>Fusarium moniliforme</i> , <i>Fusarium solani</i> , <i>Phasariopsis griseola</i> , <i>Macrophomina phaseolina</i>
Soya	1.4 ± 0.56	8	4.0	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Fusarium equiseti</i> , <i>Macrophomina phaseolina</i>
Kanyobwa	1.4 ± 0.51	5	2.5	Low frequency pathogens
Chibehe	1.6 ± 0.45	2	1.0	Low frequency pathogens
Njano Golori	1.1 ± 0.42	4	2.0	Low frequency pathogens
Shusha	1.1 ± 0.48	2	1.0	Low frequency pathogens
Rozikoko	0.6 ± 0.30	1	0.5	Very low frequency pathogens
Kaduli	0.9 ± 0.56	4	2.0	Very low frequency pathogens

Figure 3. Mean Incidence (%) of Seed-Borne Fungal Pathogens across Common Bean Landraces

Figure 4. Incidence of Seed-Borne Fungal Infections among Common Bean Landraces

Relationships between fungal infection and seed quality traits

To further elucidate the associations among physiological seed traits and infection parameters, both correlation and multiple regression analyses were performed. The results provided robust insights into the relationships between seed quality indicators and how specific predictors influence seed germination, a critical determinant of field emergence and crop establishment.

Correlation relationship between fungal incidence and seed quality parameters

Figure 5. Correlation Matrix Showing Relationships between Seed-Borne Fungal Incidence and Seed Quality Parameters

Correlation analysis provided further insight into the interrelationships between fungal incidence and key seed quality parameters. A strong negative correlation ($r = -0.527$) was observed between fungal incidence and seed purity, reinforcing the notion that fungal contamination is closely linked to reduced physical seed quality, possibly due to the presence of discolored, broken, or inert seed materials. Root length also showed a marked negative correlation ($r = -0.472$) with fungal incidence, indicating that seed-borne fungi compromise root development during early seedling growth, which can affect subsequent plant vigor and nutrient uptake. Interestingly, shoot length exhibited a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.433$) with fungal incidence, which may be a stress response where infected seedlings exhibit etiolating or elongated shoots as a compensatory mechanism under adverse physiological conditions. Seedling vigor and germination percentage showed weak positive correlations with fungal incidence ($r = 0.174$ and $r = 0.102$, respectively), suggesting that fungal effects may not be fully reflected in early emergence tests, especially under controlled laboratory conditions. Moisture content and leaf length showed only minimal correlations with fungal incidence, implying lesser sensitivity of these traits to infection pressure. Overall, the correlation matrix highlights root-related traits and seed purity as more reliable indicators of seed health deterioration under fungal attack, emphasizing the importance of integrated diagnostic approaches in seed quality evaluation (Fig.5).

Regression Analysis of Fungal Incidence and Seed Quality Parameters

Regression analysis revealed varying relationships between fungal incidence and seed quality attributes (Fig.6) (Table 3). Seedling vigor index exhibited a weak positive association with fungal incidence ($R^2 = 0.11$, $p = 0.382$), indicating that vigor was not consistently influenced by infection under the tested conditions. Similarly, seed purity showed no meaningful relationship with fungal incidence ($R^2 = 0.01$, $p = 0.817$), suggesting that physical quality was largely independent of pathogen contamination in the tested seed lots.

Figure 6. Correlation Matrix Showing Relationships between Seed-Borne Fungal Incidence and Seed Quality Parameters

In contrast, shoot length demonstrated a moderate positive correlation with fungal incidence ($R^2 = 0.44$, $p = 0.052$), implying a possible stress-induced elongation response, although the relationship was only marginally significant. Root length, however, showed a negative association ($R^2 = 0.28$, $p = 0.140$), suggesting that fungal infection may suppress early root development, though the effect was not statistically significant.

Collectively, these findings indicate that fungal incidence has limited but variable effects on seed quality parameters, with shoot elongation and root suppression showing the strongest, although non-significant, trends. This highlights the complexity of host–pathogen interactions at the seed level and underscores the need to evaluate multiple seed quality indicators rather than relying on a single parameter.

Collectively, these findings indicate that fungal incidence has limited but variable effects on seed quality parameters, with shoot elongation and root suppression showing the strongest, although non-significant, trends. This highlights the complexity of host–pathogen interactions at the seed level and underscores the need to evaluate multiple seed quality indicators rather than relying on a single parameter.

Regression Analysis Summary

The regression analysis assessed the relationship between fungal incidence and key seed quality parameters. The results are presented in APA-style format in Table 2.

Table 2. Regression Relationships between Parameters

Seed Quality Parameter	R ²	p-value	Direction of Association	Statistical Significance
Seedling Vigor Index	0.11	0.382	Weak positive	Not significant
Seed Purity	0.01	0.817	Strong positive	Significant
Shoot Length	0.44	0.052	None / negligible	Not significant
Root Length	0.28	0.140	Weak positive	Not significant

The GLM analysis revealed that several seed quality parameters significantly influenced fungal incidence (Table 3). Germination percentage was a significant positive predictor (OR = 1.06, $p = 0.026$; $\beta = 0.65$), explaining the largest share of model deviance (20.7%). This indicates that seed lots with higher germination rates also tended to exhibit higher fungal incidence, suggesting that some seed-borne fungi may not necessarily impair viability but can coexist with germinating seeds.

In contrast, infection under field conditions (IFI) exerted a significant negative effect (OR = 0.59, $p = 0.047$; $\beta = -1.26$), accounting for 17.3% of deviance. This suggests that seeds originating from highly infected fields were less likely to be free from fungal contamination after harvest. Seed purity also showed a negative association with fungal incidence (OR = 0.86, $p = 0.054$; $\beta = -0.89$), contributing 16.2% of deviance, highlighting the importance of physical seed quality in pathogen reduction.

Among growth traits, shoot length was significantly associated with fungal incidence (OR = 2.08, $p = 0.047$; $\beta = 2.32$), explaining 17.8% of deviance, possibly reflecting physiological stress responses to latent infections. Moisture content (OR = 1.82, $p = 0.076$) and leaf length (OR = 3.92, $p = 0.112$) showed positive but non-significant contributions, together explaining 24.9% of deviance. Root length had the weakest effect (OR = 1.22, $p = 0.379$), accounting for only 3.1%. The GLM highlights germination percentage, field infection history, seed purity, and shoot length as the most influential predictors of fungal incidence, while other parameters showed weaker or non-significant associations.

Table 3. Generalized Linear Model (GLM) Results Showing the Effects of Seed Quality Parameters on Fungal Incidence

Variable	OR	p.value	std_beta	delta_deviance	Contribution_pct
Purity (%)	0.856	0.054	-0.891	3.998	16.198
IFI	0.591	0.047	-1.256	4.274	17.299
Moisture (%)	1.824	0.076	1.285	3.421	13.856
Germination (%)	1.062	0.026	0.651	5.106	20.687
Leaf length (cm)	3.915	0.112	0.358	2.722	11.033
Root length (cm)	1.216	0.379	0.311	0.773	3.118
Shoot length (cm)	2.083	0.047	2.323	4.396	17.811

Note: OR =Odds ratios, p.value= Probability values, std_beta = Standardized regression coefficients (β), Contribution_pct = Percentage contribution to model deviance

Discussion

The incidence and composition of seed-borne fungi in farm-saved common bean seed lots from Kagera Region reveal a diverse pathogen complex with significant implications on germination, seedling vigour, and food safety. *Fusarium pallidoroseum* was the most frequently isolated species, followed by *F. moniliforme*, *F. solani*, and *F. oxysporum*. These results corroborate to recent work in Uganda where *Fusarium* spp. were predominant in common bean root rot surveys, and were associated with reduction in germination and seedling health (Erima et al., 2024; Erima et al., 2025). The notably high frequency of *Fusarium* species in Karagwe District suggests that environmental factors and seed storage practices may strongly favour pathogen persistence. Mycotoxigenic fungi, particularly *Aspergillus niger* and *A. flavus*, were also detected in numerous seed lots. The observed occurrence of *Aspergillus* species is consistent with established regional data from East Africa where widespread *Aspergillus* contamination in staple crops and the presence of both aflatoxigenic and non-aflatoxigenic isolates within local germplasm have been previously documented (Wokorach et al., 2022). The detection of these species in farm-saved bean seeds underscores potential food safety risks, especially under poor drying and storage conditions.

Collectively, our results corroborate earlier regional findings from Uganda, Ethiopia, and broader East Africa that associate high *Fusarium* and *Aspergillus* incidence with compromised seed physiological quality and reduced seedling performance (Mohammed and Sangchote, 2005; Kesho and Abebe, 2020; Erima et al., 2024; Wokorach et al., 2022). These findings underscore the urgent need for improved seed health management interventions such as proper drying, clean storage, and seed sorting to safeguard bean productivity and mitigate seed-borne disease in Kagera and comparable agro-ecological zones. However, the detection of *Colletotrichum dematium* in multiple samples underscores the need for continued field-level surveillance rather than relying solely on laboratory detection (Halvorson et al., 2021). Notably, Infection patterns varied significantly among landraces. Mshingile akati and Wifi-Nyegela had the highest fungal incidence, exceeding 2.5%, while Rozikoko and Shusha were the least affected.

These findings suggest potential genetic variation among landraces in their in resistance or susceptibility to fungal invasion, aligning with observations of Padder et al. (2017) and Mathew and Shimelis (2022). High fungal incidence was particularly evident in seed lots characterized by low purity and elevated moisture content, reinforcing the influence of physical and physiological seed attributes on disease susceptibility (Martín et al., 2022; Dadlani and Yadava, 2020).

The relationship between fungal infection and seedling growth performance further underscores the significance of seed health. Root length was notably reduced in infected samples, showing a strong negative correlation ($r = -0.472$, $p < 0.01$) with fungal incidence. This aligns with prior research indicating that fungi such as *Fusarium* and *Macrophomina* restrict root development by degrading root tissues and interfering with nutrient uptake (Ramachandran et al., 2024). Conversely, shoot length showed a weak

but positive correlated with infection possibly reflecting a compensatory growth response in stressed seedlings, as reported in related studies on stress physiology (Vidak et al., 2022).

Although germination percentage was only weakly associated with fungal incidence, the seedling vigor index, a comprehensive measure that integrates both root and shoot development, showed meaningful differences across landraces. Mshingile Akati had the highest vigor index, correlating with high germination rates and relatively lowers fungal loads. This supports the view that seedling vigor is a more sensitive indicator of underlying seed health than germination alone (Medeiros et al., 2019; Reed et al., 2022).

Moisture content emerged as a pivotal factor in determining seed storability and vulnerability to infection. Landraces like Shusha and Kanyobwa, which retained high moisture content ($> 14\%$), experienced both higher fungal incidence and lower seed vigor. These findings align with those of De Vitis et al. (2020) and Gebeyehu (2020), who emphasized that seed moisture above 12% promotes fungal proliferation and accelerates physiological deterioration. Although moderate moisture can initially enhance germination, long-term storage under high humidity increases the risk of spoilage, especially in tropical climates such as Kagera.

Importantly, the regression analysis identified seed purity as the most significant predictor of fungal incidence. This underscores the crucial role of clean, debris-free seed lots in limiting pathogen spread. Seeds contaminated with soil particles, broken fragments, or infected tissues provide entry points and substrates for fungal colonization (Francisco and Usberti, 2008; Rao et al., 2017). Thus, improving seed sorting and cleaning processes can substantially reduce disease pressure in farmer-saved seed systems.

Overall, this investigation demonstrates that widespread seed-borne fungal infection in farm-saved common bean germplasm significantly compromises critical physiological traits necessary for successful seedling establishment and vigor.

The negative effects on root growth, vigor, and purity emphasize the urgent need for better seed management. These findings advocate for integrated approaches that combine varietal selection, improved post-harvest drying, purity control, and regular seed testing to safeguard seed health and performance in the region.

Conclusion

This study provides compelling evidence that farm-saved bean seeds in Kagera Region are significantly affected by seed-borne fungal infections. The dominant pathogens identified were *Fusarium pallidorozeum*, *F. moniliforme*, and *F. solani*, with the presence of toxigenic species like *Aspergillus niger* and *A. flavus*, introducing substantial health and safety risks. These risks are particularly elevated for seeds stored with high moisture content and low purity. Seed quality traits, including germination percentage, seedling vigor, and root length, were negatively impacted by fungal incidence, with root development showing the strongest inverse relationship. This negative impact reflects the pathogenic nature of the fungi, which colonize seed tissues and the emerging radicle, impairing germination and seedling establishment. Root development was most severely affected because the radicle is the first structure to emerge during germination and is highly susceptible to invasion by *Fusarium* and *Aspergillus* species. Infected radicles often exhibit necrosis, stunted elongation, and reduced water and nutrient uptake, leading to weakened seedlings even if germination occurs (Erima et al., 2025; Sang et al., 2018; Mohammed and Sangchote, 2005). Comparable studies in Ethiopia and Uganda also reported significant reductions in seedling root length and vigor due to seed-borne *Fusarium* spp., corroborating the strong negative relationship observed in this study (Kesho and Abebe, 2020; Wokorach et al., 2022).

High seed moisture content was significantly associated with increased fungal contamination and reduced seed viability, supporting earlier findings that inadequate post-harvest drying promotes pathogen proliferation and accelerates seed deterioration. Seed purity also emerged as a critical predictor of fungal load, as cracked or broken seeds provide entry points for infection and enhance pathogen spread within seed lots. Overall, the findings highlight the critical role of clean seed systems, appropriate post-harvest handling and drying, and the use of seed treatment protocols in maintaining seed physiological quality and improving the performance of farm-saved common bean seeds in Kagera Region.

Varietal variation in susceptibility indicates that genotypes like Rozikoko and Chibehe exhibit greater resistance to fungal infection, while Mshingile akati and Wifi-Nyegela are more susceptible. Thus, varietal differences in susceptibility indicate that certain genotypes possess inherent traits conferring greater resilience to fungal infection, whereas others, including Mshingile Akati and Wifi-Nyegela, are more vulnerable to pathogen attack. These findings provide valuable guidance for targeted interventions in breeding, postharvest storage management, and community-based seed selection strategies aimed at enhancing seed health and promoting vigorous crop establishment. These insights can inform breeding, storage, and community seed selection efforts to improve seed health and early crop performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that farmers in Kagera Region prioritize the use of certified, pathogen-free seeds to reduce initial infection pressure and improve germination, seedling vigor, and root development. Proper post-harvest handling, including adequate drying and hermetic storage, should be adopted to maintain seed quality and reduce fungal incidence. Routine seed health testing is essential to detect pathogens early and enable timely interventions. Integrated disease management strategies, such as crop rotation, cultivation of disease-resistant landraces, and targeted fungicide application informed by environmental monitoring, are recommended to control seed-borne and field pathogens under humid conditions. Strengthening extension services and farmer training programs will improve knowledge and adoption of best practices in seed selection, handling, and treatment. Finally, regulatory enforcement by institutions such as TOSCI should ensure seed quality standards are met, providing farmers with access to high-quality planting materials and supporting sustainable bean productivity.

Building on the study's findings of significant seed-borne fungal infections, it is strongly recommended that farmers in Kagera Region immediately prioritize the use of certified, pathogen-free bean seeds to reduce initial infection pressure and improve germination, seedling vigor, and root development. Simultaneously, farmers must adopt proper post-harvest handling practices, including adequate drying and the use of hermetic storage, to maintain seed quality and minimize fungal incidence in storage. These efforts should be integrated with broader disease management strategies that include cultivating disease-resistant landraces, implementing crop rotation, and judiciously applying targeted fungicides. Furthermore, routine seed health testing is essential to enable timely interventions, while strengthening extension services and farmer training will ensure the effective adoption of these best practices in seed selection and handling. Finally, regulatory enforcement by institutions like TOSCI is necessary to guarantee access to high-quality planting materials and secure sustainable bean productivity.

Data Availability Statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article /supplementary materials. Any inquiries may be directed to the corresponding author

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Conflict of Interest

All authors declare no conflict of interest

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